

Effect of Nano ZnO on the Properties of PP/ZnO Composite Yarns

II – Thermal and Mechanical Properties

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is the modification of PP with nano ZnO at a loading of 1,2 and 3% and determination of the influence of the additive on the thermal and mechanical properties of the composites yarns.

PP/ nano composite yarns were obtained by using a twin screw extruder at 180 -220 °C (Haak Thermo Prism) and then ,the spinning of the continuous multi-filaments was done on a pilot (Spin Boy 1 machine) for production of continuous yarns at a draw ratio 3 . DSC analysis was performed to obtain melt, crystallization temperatures and degree of crystallinity for the yarns. TGA confirmed the increased thermal stability of the composites by addition of nano ZnO.

The mechanical properties were performed to obtain tensile strength and tenacity of the composites. Due to the stiff structure of the metal oxides, all tensile properties were decreased except for 1% ZnO. This is probably due to ZnO nano particles agglomerated in some regions of the matrix which was confirmed by SEM and also the results of lower degree of crystallization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymers reinforced with nano metal oxides open new pathways for flexible composites that exhibit better mechanical and chemical properties. Altan et al¹ have studied the tensile properties of PP /metal oxide nano composites prepared by using twin screw extruder of 1%, 3% and 5% TiO₂ and ZnO with polypropylene nano particles which were coated with maleic anhydride grafted styrene, butylenes and silane respectively prior melt mixing for better surface adhesion and fine dispersion. Thermal analysis was done to obtain melt and crystallization temperatures and degree of crystallinity. Then, tensile tests were done to obtain yield strength, tensile strength, elastic modulus and elongation of the composites¹. TiO₂ gave higher yield strength, tensile strength and elastic modulus due to its stiff structure and also its higher hardness than that of ZnO. On the other hand, elongation of the PP/TiO₂ composites was expected to be lower when compared with ZnO reinforced composites.

Three polypropylene (PP)/ ZnO nano composites² containing 5, 10 and 15 wt% nano particles were prepared through melt-blending. Compression molded samples were used for dynamic mechanical and morphological studies. The nano ZnO particles were observed to be dispersed uniformly, but with a different level of coalescence, by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

All tensile properties of nano composites with except the elongation were increased. PP / ZnO particles agglomerated in some regions of the matrix confirm the results of lower elongation and degree of crystallization.

Polypropylene /nano clay composite monofilaments were produced at (1,2,3% nanoclay) and (10,15&20% compatilizer) using single screw extruder. It was observed that tensile stress of composite monofilament decreased compared to pure polypropylene monofilament. Melting temperature and degree of crystallinity were not affected much; however, there was significant increase at decomposition temperature of composite polypropylene mono-filaments³.

The effect of ZnO nanoparticles on the structure and properties of common thermoplastic polymers (polyoxymethylene (POM), polypropylene (PP), ethylene- α -octene copolymers (EOC)) and their binary blends is investigated. EOC content in the composites varies from 0 to 50 wt. %. The amount of nano structured ZnO filler in the composites is changed in the interval from 0 to 5 wt. %. Tensile and frictional properties of ZnO modified nano composites are investigated. Results of the article show that ZnO additions cause increment in stiffness and strength as well as coefficient of friction for the nano composites. The effect of ZnO modifier is the highest at low EOC content. The effect of ZnO is strongly dependent on the compatibility and crystallinity of the nano composites. Nano structured ZnO filler is used in variety of applications due to its photocatalytic reactions, self-purification, antibacterial and other properties. It has been shown that ZnO increases thermal stability^{4,5}, mechanical stiffness and strength⁵ of certain composites, as well as decreases their coefficient of friction. In these studies, however, pure polymers are used as matrices. Meanwhile, there is practically no information about polymer blend usage as matrix for ZnO modified polymer nano composites. Melt spinning of polypropylene fibers containing nano silver and zinc particles were investigated by Gawish et al⁶ and others⁷. The nano metals were generally uniformly dispersed in polypropylene, but aggregation of these materials was observed on fibers surface and in fibers cross-sections. The mechanical properties of the resulted composite fibers with low concentration of nano metal were comparable to those for the control PP yarns. Extruded composite fibers that contained 0.72% silver and 0.60% zinc nano particles had outstanding antibacterial efficacy as documented by the percentage count reduction growth of

Escherichia coli and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Fibers containing silver particles had improved antistatic properties. The newly synthesized PP/ Ag nonwoven fabric dressing enhances, promotes and plays an important role on incisional wound healing in rats⁸. Effects of ZnO nano particles on the mechanical and antibacterial properties of polyurethane coatings were studied.⁹ PP/TiO₂ composite fibers were prepared by melt compounding and sputter coating¹⁰.

In our previous investigation¹⁰, we prepared composite PP yarns containing 1-3 % nano ZnO loading and studied the UV blocking properties and confirmed that the PP/3% ZnO yarns gave the best UV protection since UPF was 89.9%. In the present research for the same yarns, study was performed for the morphological, the thermal (DSC, TGA) and mechanical properties of these yarns (tensile strength and tenacity).

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Nano ZnO 20 (particle size 30 nm) was supplied from Unicore Zinc chemical (Belgium). The spin finish was Crosamol IPA07, purchased from Euro dye CTC.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Extrusion and spinning of PP and 1,2,3 % nano ZnO/PP composites

- The extrusion of PP yarns and PP / 1,2,3 % nano ZnO were done on a thermo Prism PTW- 16 (Thermo Haak, England) which is a twin melt compounding rotating extruder working at 180-220°C.
- The spinning of fibers was effected at (200-230 °C) on a pilot laboratory spin boy 1 (Buss heart Engineering, Germany), which is a single screw extruder producing multi-filaments at draw ratio 3, continuous yarns of 80 filaments, 148Tex. After extrusion, the yarns are finished with the spin finish.

2.2.2 Thermal Properties of PP/ nano ZnO yarns

- **Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)**

A compensated differential scanning calorimeter (DSC Perkin-Elmer Model 7) equipped with a cooler was used under nitrogen flow. All samples were heated from 25 to 200°C at a rate of 10°C /min. From the DSC graphs, melting temperatures (T_m) of the nano composite fibers were obtained and the apparent fusion enthalpies were calculated from the area of the endothermic peak. The degree of crystallinity of polypropylene was evaluated using the following equation:

$$X = \frac{\Delta H}{\Delta H_f} 100 \%$$

where X is the degree of crystallinity, ΔH_f the enthalpy heat of fusion for PP fibers and ΔH_f° the enthalpy heat of fusion of 100% crystalline PP taken as 209 J/g

- **Thermal gravimetric Analysis (TGA)**

TGA was measured for PP blank and PP/1-3 % nano ZnO composite using a Shimadzu TGA-50H operated under nitrogen atmosphere at Cairo University.

The percentage residual weight versus temperature was evaluated at a scan rate 10C/min over a temperature range 25-600 °C.

- **Mechanical Properties**

The fibers count number (Tex) was calculated at the testing laboratory by the skein method according to ASTM-D1907 after conditioning the fibers at 20°C and 65% RH for 24 h. The strain at break and tenacity were determined from 25 to 450 °C according to ASTM-D2256.

- **Morphological Observations**

Morphology study for the yarn was characterized by a scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples were placed on the SEM stubs using a two-sided adhesive tape and then, SEM analyses using a LEO Gemini 1530 field emission SEM was carried out at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV after Pt sputtering.

3 RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

- **Morphological Observations**

SEM shows (Fig. 1) some nano ZnO agglomeration on the yarns surface.

Figure 1: SEM of PP/3% nano ZnO composite yarns (500 X).

- **Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC)**

Sample	Peak melting T_m (°C)	Enthalpy ΔH_f (J/g)	Crystallinity (X %)
pp Blank	165.27	97.05	46.44
PP/2%ZnO	164.24	95.62	45.75
PP/3%ZnO	164.28	89.51	42.83

Table 1: DSC properties of PP / nano ZnO composite yarns.

Thermo grams of PP and PP/nano ZnO composites are shown in Table 1 which include the melting points heat of fusion ΔH and the percentage crystallinity. DSC study shows that the

melting temperatures slightly decreased to 164.24 and 146.28° C by one degree by the addition of 2 or 3% nano ZnO composite compared to 165.27° C for the blank.

The crystallinity decreased from 46.44 % for the blank to 45.75% for PP/2% nano ZnO and 42.83 % for PP/ 3% nano ZnO

- **Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)**

Temperature °C	Blank residual wt %	PP/1%nanoZnO, residual wt %	PP/2%nanoZn residual wt %	PP/3%nanoZnO residual wt %
300	83.44	93.42	92.99	94.4
350	63.3	61.7	70.87	72.67
400	2.15	4.6	16.01	10.2
450	1.7	3.77	13.08	1.4

Table 2: TGA, Effect of temperature on the residual weight of PP/ nano ZnO composite yarns

The increased thermal stability of PP/nano ZnO composite yarns have been measured, confirmed and compared with that of PP blank yarns, as a function of temperature (T °C) and the percentage residual weight in the range 25-600 °C Decomposition temperatures of the composite yarn are shown on Table 2 and the percentage residual weight graphs are illustrated in (Figure 2)

Upon increasing the percentage nano ZnO for PP from 1-3% the decomposition temperature was shifted from 300 °C (83.44% residual weight) for the blank to 450 °C(13.08% residual weight) creating a more thermally stable fabric . The stability of the composite yarns at 400 °C is as follows:

PP/2%nanoZnO (16.01 residual weight) > PP/3%nanoZnO (10.2% residual weight) > PP/1% nano ZnO (4.6% residual weight) > Blank (2.15%residual weight)

Figure 2: TGA, Effect of temperature on the residual weigh of PP/nano ZnO composite yarns

- **Mechanical Properties**

Addition of 1% nano ZnO to PP increases the breaking force to 29.38N compared to 28.03N for the blank indicating the formation of a strong PP/1% nano ZnO composite. Further addition of 2% or 3% nano ZnO to PP decreased the breaking force to 25.36N and 20.51N respectively. The same behavior was remarked for the fiber tenacity which was 0.1985 N/Tex for PP/1%ZnO compared 0.1894N/Tex for the blank .Then, the fiber tenacity decreased to 0.1714for PP/2% ZnO and 0.1386 N/Tex for PP/3% ZnO.

Sample	Count (tex)	Breaking force (N)	Fiber tenacity N/tex	SD for fiber tenacity
pp control	148	28.03	0.1894	0.0056
PP/1%ZnO	148	29.38	0.1985	0.0070
PP/2%ZnO	148	25.36	0.1714	0.0026
PP/3%ZnO	148	20.51	0.1386	0.003

Table 3: Mechanical properties of PP / ZnO composite fibers

- **Antibacterial activity**

The sample PP/3% nano ZnO composite and others acquired a yellowish colour compared to the blank which was white after spin finishing. The microbiological analysis of the sample against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia Coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*, doesn't give any antimicrobial activity on the tested microorganisms.

It was believed even after extraction of the sample with petroleum ether, that a side reaction was happened between nano ZnO particles of the sample and the spin finish used (Crosamol IPA07), this problem should be further studied and resolved between the spin finish Producer and Ensait University in France.

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